

Patient Prompts

Migraine

Patient's Full Name	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Pete Mitchell (Male) Penny Benjamin (Female) 	Palliating factors <i>"What makes the pain better?"</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Resting in a dark/quiet room Taking ibuprofen (Advil) tablets as soon as the headache starts
Patient's Age	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 36 years old 	Quality <i>"What type of pain is it?"</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Pounding/throbbing pain Sharp pain
Patient's DOB	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> May 16 in 1986 	Region <i>"Could you show me where it hurts?"</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The whole right side of my head
Vital Signs: <u>No need to memorize!</u>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Temp: 98°F BP: 122/78 mmHg HR: 84/min, regular RR: 18/min 	Radiation <i>"Does the pain move anywhere else?"</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The pain does not move/radiate anywhere else
Chief Complaint <i>"How can I help you today?"</i>	<i>"I have a terrible headache."</i>	Severity <i>"On a scale of one to ten, how severe is the pain now?"</i> <i>"How about when the pain started?"</i> <i>"Does it affect your daily life?"</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Now, the pain is a 6/10 When the pain first started it was an 8/10 It is affecting my job performance
Open ended question <i>"Could you tell me more about the pain?"</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> "This particular headache started about 3 days ago. However, I've had several similar headaches on and off for the past year." 	Timing <i>"How long have you had the pain for?"</i> <i>"Do you have it all the time or does it come and go?"</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Has had the pain for the past 2 days It comes and goes
Onset <i>"When did it start?"</i> <i>"What were you doing when the pain started?"</i> <i>"Did the pain start suddenly or gradually?"</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 3 days ago Was commuting home from work on the train when it started Started gradually 	Associated Symptoms (unchecked items are all negative) When you are asked "Do you have any other symptoms?," please say " <u>Such as?</u> " <u>Please mention only when asked specifically!</u> If they use medical terms, please say " <u>What's that?</u> " These associated symptoms started 3 days ago, the same time as the headache.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> vomiting <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> feeling nauseated <input type="checkbox"/> fever <input type="checkbox"/> feeling drowsy <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> loss of appetite <input type="checkbox"/> sleepiness <input type="checkbox"/> double vision/blind spots <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> seeing flashing lights prior to the headache <input type="checkbox"/> watery eyes <input type="checkbox"/> numbness <input type="checkbox"/> feeling pins & needles <input type="checkbox"/> muscle weakness <input type="checkbox"/> loss of coordinated movements <input type="checkbox"/> difficulty in speaking <input type="checkbox"/> ear ringing <input type="checkbox"/> feeling the room is spinning <input type="checkbox"/> drooping upper eyelids <input type="checkbox"/> runny nose <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> sensitivity to lights <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> sensitivity to noise <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> sensitivity to smell <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> feeling strange before the headache starts
Before the onset <i>"What were you doing before the pain started?"</i> <i>"Have you ever had the same symptoms before?"</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Working at the office Has had several similar headaches in the past year 		
After the onset <i>"Do you have any other symptoms?"</i> <i>"Have you taken any medications to treat the pain?"</i> <i>"Have you already seen a doctor about this?"</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> I have... (see the Associated Symptoms to the right) I take ibuprofen (Advil) tablets when I get the pain which seem to help somewhat but only if I take them as soon as the headache starts. No, I haven't seen any doctors before you. 		
Provoking Factors <i>"What make the pain worse?"</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Routine physical activities Bright lights Noise 		

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<p>Past Medical History</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “Have you ever had any health problems in the past?” • “Have you ever had any checkup abnormalities?” • “Have you ever had any major injuries in the past?” 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Childhood asthma: No longer an issue since age 10 	<p>Social History: Home Situation, Occupation & Travel</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “Do you live alone or with somebody else?” • “Are you currently working?” • “Have you travelled recently?” 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lives with boyfriend/ girlfriend • Currently works as a pharmaceutical sales rep at a drug company • Hasn’t travelled recently
<p>Past Surgical History</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “Have you ever had any surgeries/operations in the past?” • Have you ever been hospitalised before?” 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • None 	<p>Social History: Alcohol</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “Do you drink alcohol?” • “What types of alcohol do you drink?” • “How many drinks do you have per week?” 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Drinks a glass of red wine on a social basis
<p>Medications</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “Are you currently on any Rx medications/ OTC medications/ supplements?” • (In the case of Rx meds) “Do you take it as the doctor prescribed?” 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • OTC meds: ibuprofen (Advil) tablets as needed for the headaches 	<p>Social History: Smoking</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “Do you smoke?” • “How many cigarettes do you smoke per day?” • “When did you start/stop smoking?” 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Doesn’t smoke now. • Used to smoke 2 cigarettes/ day during university (for about 4 years)
<p>Allergies</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “Are you allergic to any medications/food/anything else?” • “What happened when you got the allergy?” 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sulfonamide allergy (had a skin rash) • Allergic rhinitis due to cedar trees (runny nose, itchy watery eyes, and sneezing) 	<p>Social History: Illicit Drugs</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “Have you ever used any recreational drugs?” 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Never
<p>OBGYN (Female Only)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “When was your last menstrual period?” • “Is there any possibility that you might be pregnant?” • “Have you ever been pregnant before?” 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Last menstrual period was three weeks ago. Has regular menstrual periods. • Unlikely that she is pregnant as she is on the copper IUD for contraception • Has never been pregnant 	<p>ROS (Review of Systems)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • As per the associated symptoms above
<p>Family History</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “Are your parents well/are your parents still with us?” • “Do any health problems run in your family?” • “Does anyone in your family have (specific disease)?” • “Does anyone in your family have similar symptoms?” 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Parents are still alive. Father (66 yo) has gout and diabetes. Mother (67 yo) has migraines, high cholesterol and “inactive thyroid” • Mother has similar symptoms 	<p>Summary</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “Do you have any questions?” • “Is there anything in particular that you are concerned about?” 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No particular questions. • I think I may be having migraines.. I am worried that if my job performance worsens because of this persistent headache. I may lose my job. So please find out what is happening as soon as possible.